

Article

The Practice of Domestic Violence in India- How to tackle it?

Indrani Ghatak*

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Abstract

The paper examined the nature and causes of violence within the family. It also highlighted some of its effects on the individual victim, the family, the society and the nation. Among such consequences are physical injuries, poor health, general emotional distress, PTSD, low self esteem, poor marital relationships and so on. The paper also discussed the prevalence rate of domestic violence and also highlighted that the crime was unreported due to various reasons in spite of the presence of several legislations. The paper discussed some state as well as non-governmental interventions that can help in managing and preventing domestic violence. It is also highly advocated in this paper that social workers and other care givers should be more committed towards solving the problems of victims of family violence or reducing its scourge in our societies.

Key words

Domestic Violence, dowry, patriarchy, PWDVA, NGO, family counseling, Social work intervention.

* JRF Scholar, Department of Sociology, University Of Burdwan

Introduction

Violence and destructive behavior are not inherent in the animal nature of human being. Such behaviors tend to occur where supportive social structures are absent and people are engulfed in fear and anxiety (Roy, 2000). Violence against women existed as an integral part of the journey of women. Violence or the threat of it, particularly at home, reduced the range of choices open to women and girls and restrained freedom in both public and private life, destroyed health, disrupted their lives, eroded self-confidence and self-esteem (Heyzer, 1998).

During the Rig-Vedic period in India, the Aryan women enjoyed privileges of education and of choosing their own partner (Sur, 1973), performed religious rituals (Jain, 1988). In the later Vedic period, the status and honorable position of a woman was gradually deteriorated and various restrictions were put on the woman's rights and privileges by "Manu". King Manu in 200 B.C wrote, in his "The Laws of Manu" that 'by a young girl, by a young woman, or even by an aged one, nothing must be done independently, even in her own house. In childhood a female must be subject to her father, in youth to her husband, when her lord is dead to her sons; a woman must never be independent'. Women was regarded as subservient to man and confined to household works and child bearing only (Jain, 1988). Medieval India was like the 'dark age' for women with foreign invasions and cultural marginalization radically transformed the position of women. Educational deprivation, early marriage, practice of Sati, complete subjugation to one's husband led to the downfall of women from being the Goddess Shakti to a mere secondary object (Mishra, 1967). During the British period, Domestic violence was found in most of the family in the name of different customs. Early marriage, enforced widowhood, female infanticide, Satipratha, Devdasi system, Dowry system, Polygamy etc were prevalent in the society (Desai, 1977). But during the British regime due to education and western impact on socio-cultural life of India, the society began to change for

the better. Gradually great social reformers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar, Dayanand Saraswati and Mahatma Gandhi, contributed to the emancipation of Indian women. Various acts like Child Marriage Restraint Act, Widow Remarriage Act, Abolition of Sati Act were passed, which took a gigantic step in elevating the conditions of women (Jain, 1988). In Post Independence India women gained political rights which helped in gaining liberation to a certain extent. Industrialization, urbanization, educational opportunities and the changing value system improved women's position in the well-to-do sections of the society (Jain, 1988) but a majority of families in India still held back on economic resources to save her gifts to the women's future husband and his family (Ghansham, 2002).

Violence against women is partly a result of gender relations that assumes men to be superior to women. Given the subordinate status of women, much of gender violence is considered normal and enjoys social sanction. Manifestations of violence include physical aggression, such as blows of varying intensity, burns, attempted hanging, sexual abuse and rape, psychological violence through insults, humiliation, coercion, blackmail, economic or emotional threats, and control over speech and actions. In extreme, but not unknown cases, death is the result. (Gardella, 2007) These expressions of violence take place in a man-woman relationship within the family, state and society. Usually, domestic aggression towards women and girls, due to various reasons remain hidden.

Precipitating factors responsible for domestic violence against women

A number of studies have been conducted to identify the causes as well as the precipitating factors which lead to domestic violence against women. There are various reasons of increasing rate of domestic violence against women like disintegration of joint families, domination by husbands towards wife causing irritations to them, extra marital relationships, undue interference of family members, alcoholism of the husbands, baseless suspicion on one's spouse, not bringing the desired amount of

dowry as expected by the groom's family, refusing sex and even for petty reasons like food not being served on time or women not being able to give ample time to her family and in-laws due to work pressure, etc (Goel, 2010).

Pandey et al (2009) made a study of 751 women, living in slums of Calcutta to examine the perspectives of men & women on partner & relationship factors of domestic violence & said that individual factors related to husbands that increased the risk of violence included poor socio-economic status, use of alcohol, extramarital relations & visiting red light districts. Kaur & Garg (2009) conducted Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) among married women showed that an alcoholic husband was the main cause for domestic violence.

Ahuja (2003:123) dwells on the various forms of ill-treatment & humiliation that take place against the victim women due to dowry demand. The methods used in ill-treating daughter-in-law/wives/sisters-in-law are 'abuse, insult, passing sarcastic remarks, assault, denial of food, attempts at starvation, prohibiting the victims from going out & meeting anyone, refusing visits to the parent's house, not permitting them to talk to visitors from the parent's home and locking them up in a room' (ibid.130). Ahuja's findings show that in some cases, the victims were tortured & beaten to the extent that it was not possible for them to walk to the hospital.

Paul's (1986) findings show that some women too wanted dowry to be given to their conjugal household to shut the mouth of the in-laws or to prevent apprehended harassment from them. For these women, it is very difficult to know the mother-in-law before hand before marriage. They also feel that the socio-economic oppression faced by the mother-in-law motivates her to oppress the new bride. Moreover, 'cultural lag' & insecurity of modern life, many a time, force the mother-in-law to find faults with the new bride. Thus, most women feel that in order to obstruct any form of torture & harassment, it is better to give a dowry.

Teja (1993) has made an attempt to investigate the differences of attitudes between te working & non-working women towards dowry. His findings show that a majority of the working & non-working

females were of the view that dowry should be given in marriage as this is the only indirect way through which females could extract their share of the parental property. Yet it was noted that the working rather than the non-working females predominantly held this view. The main reason for demanding dowry in marriage according to working & non-working females was a desire 'to become rich overnight'.

Jejeebhoy (1998) is of the view that not only wife beating is deeply entrenched, but also people justify it. Thus, domestic violence is simply not a personal abnormality but rather it roots in the cultural norms of the family and the society. Again, looking from another angle, it is found that many of the victims of domestic violence has either refused to name the perpetrator of the assault or attributed the injuries to other reasons (Daga et al., 1999).

There is no single factor to account for violence perpetrated against women. Increasingly, research has focused on the inter-relatedness of various factors that should improve our understanding of the problem within different cultural contexts. Several complex & interconnected institutionalized social & cultural factors have kept women particularly vulnerable to the violence directed at them, all of them manifestations of historically unequal power relations between men & women. Factors contributing to these unequal power relations include socio-economic forces, the family institution where power relations are enforced, fear of & control over female sexuality, belief in the inherent superiority of males & legislations & cultural sanctions that have traditionally denied women & children an independent legal & social status.

Consequences of domestic violence

Studies show that women who reported higher rates of abuse had higher levels of stress, depression and physical health symptoms compared with women who had no or lower rates of abuse (Sutherland et al, 2002). The results showed that 70% of the abused women had faced health hazards. Cuts, bruises, broken homes and burns were the most common

injuries faced. According to a study by the US state department for justice it has been noticed that 37% of all women who went to the emergency section in the hospital had gone for violence related injuries and had been hurt by their spouses (UNICEF, 2000). A study in South India also found that 34% of the women reported of abuse from their husbands and needed medical attention (Rao, 1997).

Women who survived domestic violence, may experience long term psychological disorders, sleep disorders, chronic depression, anxiety, paranoia, drug and alcohol dependence, eating disorders and some short-term physical and emotional problems, such as maternal depression, suicidal tendencies, preoccupation with the violence, emotional withdrawal, irritability, feelings of hopelessness or an inability to adequately respond to the needs of their children (D'Ambrosio, 2008). About 97% of the survivors had lost mental peace and were under stress and anxiety incessantly. About 97% of the survivors believed that they had no hope in life. Suicidal tendency was one of the most common mental health consequences of spousal violence (Sutherland et al, 2002). In numerous studies Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and depression have been associated with spousal violence and their consequences have been found to be quite long term and damaging to the overall mental health of the survivor (Chandra et al, 2009).

An important dimension of the consequences of spousal violence was its economic implications. Abused women were more likely to have experienced unemployment and also had lower personal income (Lloyd, 1997).

As per Unicef's (2000) understanding, the most crucial consequences of domestic violence against women is the denial of fundamental human rights to women. Women, who are the victims of domestic violence, are being deprived of the right to protection from gender-based abuse and neglect. There is a growing recognition that countries cannot reach their full potential as long as women's potential to participate fully in their society is denied. In this sense, domestic violence undermines progress towards human and economic development .

Prevalence of domestic violence in the world

Domestic violence is a serious problem around the world. Around the world, at least one in three women has been beaten, coerced into sex or otherwise abused during her lifetime (Heise, 1999). According to WHO report worldwide, 40-70% of all female murder victims are killed by their intimate partner.

In United States, women are six times more likely than men to be victims of intimate partner violence. In 92% of domestic violence incidents, crimes are committed against women by men. About 4 million women in the USA experience a serious assault by an intimate partner during a 12 month's period.

In Egypt, 35% of women are beaten by their husbands, in Nicaragua 52% are abused by their partners at least once. In Canada 29% were at 12,300 women were reported being physically assaulted by a current or a former partner.

In Japan 59% of 796 women were reported being beaten by their partners. In Kenya 42% of 612 women were reported being beaten by their partners. In Zimbabwe 32% of 966 women reported of being physically abused by their partners. 29% of women in Romania, 22% in Russia and 21% in Ukraine reported experience of spousal physical abuse (Astra Network, 1999).

In 2000, the proportions of women who are reported to be attempted or completed forced sex with an intimate partner were Brazil 10%, Peru 46.7%, and Thailand 29.9%. The proportions of women reported of being physically assaulted by an intimate partner were 34% in Egypt, 10% in Paraguay, 22% in U.S.A. In Canada 62% of women murdered, died at the hands of their intimate male partners (World Report on Violence and Health, 2002).

In 2004 British Crime Survey (BCS) found that there were an estimated 12.9 million incidents of domestic violence against women in England and Wales. Every minute in the U.K, the police receive a call from the public for assistance for domestic violence. This leads to police receiving as estimated 1300 calls each day or over 570000 each year. According to the British Crime Survey, only 40.2%

of actual domestic violence crimes are reported to the police (Women Aid Federation of England).

Domestic violence is widespread in Europe. In France, six women die each month at the hands of their spouse. In Spain, some 100 women are killed each year by abusive spouses or boyfriends and there are over 30000 complaints of physical violence. In Switzerland, one in five women is affected by physical and sexual violence in their lifetime. More precisely more than one in eight women suffers physical violence while one in nine suffers sexual violence (Naravane, 2004).

In this context it is also stated that today stalking is a very popular form of domestic violence in many foreign countries like U.K, U.S.A etc. In U.S.A 78% of stalking victims are women (Centre for Policy Research, 1997). Many anti stalking legislations were enacted by different states. Marital Rape is also considered as domestic violence in many foreign countries. In many Latin American countries which have enacted legislation for preventing Marital rape as domestic violence are Argentine, Bolivia, Chile, Columbia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, El Salvador, Mexico, Nicaragua, Peru, Puerto Rico, Namibia, South Africa, U.S.A etc (UNICEF, 2000).

Prevalence of Domestic Violence in India:

India's National Family Health Survey- III, carried out in 29 states during 2005-2006, has found that a substantial proportion of married women have been physically or sexually abused by their husbands at some time in their lives. The survey indicated that, nationwide, 37.2% of women "experienced violence" after marriage. Bihar was found to be the most violent, with the abuse rate against married women being as high as 59%. Strangely, 63% of these incidents were reported from urban families rather than the state's most backward villages. It was followed by Madhya Pradesh (45.8%), Rajasthan (46.3%), Manipur (43.9%), Uttar Pradesh (42.4%), Tamil Nadu (41.9%) & West Bengal (40.3%).

Statistics reveal that a total number of 203804 incidents of crime against women both under Indian Penal Code (IPC) were reported in the country during 2009 as compared to 186617 during 2008. Again in 2010, the figure is 213585 which increased to 244270

in 2012. Over the years, the percentage of crime against women in total crimes under the Indian Penal Code has risen. In the year 2007, cruelty by husband and relatives accounted for more than one third of the total crimes against women, the highest share among all the crimes against women in India followed by molestation which formed about 20.43%. Apparently, women who consider it unsafe to venture out for employment or education are often unaware that they might not be completely safe in their homes as well.

Table No.1. Proportion of Crime against women (IPC) towards total IPC crimes

Serial number	Year	Total IPC Crimes	Crime against women (IPC cases)	Percentage to IPC crimes
1	2008	209337	18661	8.9
2	2009	212134	20380	9.2
3	2010	222483	21358	9.6
4	2011	232557	21914	9.4
5	2012	238718	24427	10.2

Source: NCRB, Government of India

The cases of 'torture' lodged under 498A of the IPC in 2011 have dramatically increased from 50,703 (2003) to 81,344 (2008) to 94041 (2010) & 106527 (2012). These are official statistics & no one knows how many cases go unreported, since the myth that wife battering is a 'private matter' has silenced many victims for centuries (Bhattacharya, 2004).

Table No.2. Cases Registered under Cruelty by Husbands or his relatives during 2006 to 2012

Year	Number of cases registered
2006	63128
2007	75930

2008	81344
2009	89546
2010	94041
2011	99135
2012	106527

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, GOI

18.7% of these were reported from West Bengal (19,865 cases) followed by Andhra Pradesh 12.6% (13,389 cases) and Rajasthan 12.5% (13,312).

Prevalence of Domestic Violence against Women in West Bengal

West Bengal is the most densely populated state in India. According to 2011 census, the population of West Bengal is 9.1 crore and according to the population of India, West Bengal is in the 4th position having sex ratio of 934 females per 1000 males. The literacy rate in West Bengal is 69.22% in 2011. The male literacy rate is 77.58% and female literacy rate is 60.22%.

Table No.3. Cases Registered & Persons arrested under IPC Sec. 498A & Dowry prohibition Act, 1961 in West Bengal

Year	Sec. 498A	Persons arrested under Sec.498A	Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961	Persons arrested under Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961
2006	7414	15354	25	27
2007	9900	14700	40	145
2008	13663	17521	68	97
2009	16112	13884	46	74
2010	17796	18387	53	142
2011	19772	17583	116	196
2012	19865	22911	241	466

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, GOI

In the year 2011, according to the recent statistics of National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB), West Bengal has occupied the 2nd position in India for domestic violence offences after Andhra Pradesh and accounted for the 4th highest dowry deaths after Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Madhya Pradesh. In the year 2012 surprisingly it was reported that with 7.5% share of the country's population, West Bengal accounted for nearly 12.7% of total crime against women by reporting 29133 cases. The NCRB figures also show that Andhra Pradesh accounting for nearly 7% of the country's population recorded 12.4% of the total crime against women with 28246 cases (The Hindu, 2012).

From 2001 to 2011, the domestic violence rate is increased to 80%. In 2001, the number of domestic violence cases in West Bengal was 3859 which is 6936 in 2006. In 2007, it is 9900 and in 2011 it is 17796. Dowry death rate is increased to 68%. In 2001, Dowry Death cases were 265 which increased to 446 in 2006 and it is 507 in 2011.

There has been a steady rise in the number of cases of violence against women by their husband and relatives in West Bengal from 2005 to 2008. The rise in the number of cases from 2005-2006 was a 6.5% but 2006-2007 saw a rise of 33% followed by a gigantic increase in 2007-2008 reaching at around 41.4% and it get increased to 68.1% from 2010-2011 (State Crime Records Bureau, West Bengal) (Pathak,2010; Sarkar, 2010) .

According to the latest data of National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB), 2011, in West Bengal, the total number of incidence of offenses against women committed in the year 2010 is 26,125, cruelty by husband and relatives accounted for more than two third of the total crimes against women (17796) which is the highest share among all the crimes against women in India.

In a recent report it has been pointed out that West Bengal recorded 30942 crime cases in 2012. They include 2046 cases of rape, 4168 cases of kidnapping, 593 cases of dowry deaths and 19865 cases of domestic cruelty. Expressing concern over the rise in Crime against women, Chairperson of the

State's Women Commission Sunanda Mukherjee, however, said that the statistics reflected a positive side. "Women are coming out in greater number to register complaints of atrocities committed against them" (The Hindu, 2013).

State intervention towards minimizing domestic violence against women

After Independence of India, the framers of the Constitution of India were conscious about the discrimination and unequal treatment of women in every field of their lives and violence against women including domestic violence. Consequently, they included certain general as well as specific provisions in the Constitution of India under Part III as "Fundamental Rights" and Part IV as "Directive Principles of State Policy" for the uplift of the status of women and also to eradicate the violence against women from the society. Article 14 and 15 of the Constitution of India recognize the dignity of women. The Constitution empowers the Parliament to enact laws in favour of women. Article 39A ensures free legal aid to the women by suitable legislation to provide opportunities to the women for securing justice. Article 51A (e) of the Constitution of India specifies that it shall be the duty of every citizen of India to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women.

Criminal & Civil Law

The issue of violence against women in India was publicly highlighted for the first time in the mid 1970s, through the campaign against dowry and related violence. The campaign led to the Criminal Law (Second Amendment) Act in 1983, which introduced Section 498A in the IPC. Under this provision, 'cruelty' to the wife by the husband or his relatives was made a cognizable, non-bailable offence punishable with imprisonment up to 3 years and a fine. Cruelty was defined as including both physical and mental cruelty and any harassment associated with the demand for dowry. Section 498A

included cases of everyday violence against women in the home within its ambit (Reddy, 2007).

Moreover, only married women facing violence at the hands of the husband or their families could claim relief under 498A. It did not protect women from violence in natal relationships or in relationships that have not received the legal sanction of marriage. The definition of cruelty posed difficulties when one tried to include issues of sexual violence, economic violence or even threats of violence within the ambit of the same. Continuous struggle by women's groups has changed the situation and ultimately Indian lawmakers have realized that domestic violence mean not only violence related to dowry but several forms of crimes.

Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA) is a comprehensive law and it addresses all issues related to women in the domestic sphere. Interestingly, as per the judgement of Bombay High Court delivered on 18th July 2009 provisions of the new Act will apply retrospectively. Hence, women can seek protection under the new Act even though they have faced violence much before it came into force in October 2006. The act has classified 'domestic violence' into four categories, namely a) physical, b) sexual, c) verbal & emotional, and d) economic violence, and attempted to define such violence comprehensively. The new Act goes beyond the 498 (A) of the IPC and extends protection to even female live-in partners. The creation of an official cadre called Protection Officers (POs) and recognition of NGOs as Service Providers (SPs) are two other salient features of the new law. The PWDVA provides opportunity for renewed and refocused efforts to address the issue of domestic violence (Ghosh B. , 2013).

Divorce

Divorce is frequently seen as the only option for women fleeing from violent husbands. However, it is often extremely difficult for women to obtain a divorce and keep her safe during the process.

Judicial responses

Police officers, lawyers and judges play an important role in the legal systems response to domestic violence. Because they are generally the final authority in civil and criminal matters involving domestic abuse, protect battered women and the batterer alike that domestic violence will not be tolerated. Judicial responses to domestic violence can, however further victim safety and batterer accountability in many ways. In the court rooms, judges are enforcers and interpreters of existing laws, they may also have the ability to establish court room policies and procedures that promote victim safety and are respectful of all parties. Outside the court rooms, judges are often community leaders and can play vital roles in the effort to eliminate domestic violence.

National Commission for Women (NCW)

In January 1992, the National Commission for Women (NCW) was set up as a statutory body under the National Commission for Women Act, 1990 to review the constitutional and legal safeguards for women, recommend remedial legislative measures and facilitate redressal of grievances and advice the government on all policy matters affecting women.

Non-governmental Intervention

Where the state has failed to ensure the availability of adequate services for victims of domestic violence, NGOs have organized to provide counseling, temporary shelters, crisis centers, and hotlines. In addition, NGOs work to coordinate the responses of community members, from legal and medical professionals to members of religious organizations, to ensure that victims' needs are met and that batterers are consistently held accountable. Finally, NGOs have adopted a variety of advocacy strategies aimed at preventing domestic violence.

Advocacy. NGOs provide a variety of support and assistance to battered women. Battered women are faced with violence, sometimes on a daily basis. Many women who seek help are ashamed of their

situation and feel responsible for what is happening to them. They need to work with advocates who understand their situation and will help them determine for themselves what they need to do. Individual advocates counsel women and assist them in providing for their own safety. Advocates with legal expertise can provide advice that is not only helpful but necessary for victims seeking relief from the court system.

To work effectively with battered women, an individual advocate need not be a psychological professional. The role of an advocate is to assist a woman in making her own decisions and providing for her own safety. Advocates must believe the women affirm their ability to address their own problems. They must respect differences in background without judging. Advocates should listen actively and assist women with problem solving. Well-trained advocates can work in paid or volunteer positions. They are an important part of serving women victims of violence (Phadnis, 1996).

Safety Planning: Women are usually the best judges of the dangers their abusers pose to them. An advocate can help a battered woman assess the risk the batterer poses to her and develop a practical plan to keep herself safe. While evaluating risks and creating safety plans can help a woman, safety planning is no guarantee that she will not be injured.

Shelters and Safe Houses: In many countries around the world, NGOs have created shelter homes to provide temporary housing and other services to battered women and their children. In India, the women facing domestic violence generally require shelter to survive.

In some countries, NGOs have begun to operate shelters with public addresses. The theory behind a public address is to acknowledge the violence in the community and to avoid adding to shame women may feel by staying hidden. Even shelters with public addresses, however, keep the identities of the individual women using their services confidential. Many NGOs are providing the victim women with short-stay homes. These homes provide shelter and food, free of cost for a short period up to six months, to these distressed women and their minor children.

Counseling services: Whenever a woman is deprived of conjugal rights or divorced or faced with domestic violence, she feels that there is no other way than to die and goes into depression. Many disheartened women often attempt to commit suicide under such circumstances. Many NGOs after being informed of those cases try to encourage the victim and promise her that they are by their side and make her feel that she is not alone. They hear her problems and give advice to follow. They give assurance to her that they will fight for her cause and provide her all sorts of assistance. They educate her by telling all the necessary legal provisions and rights to fight for. They also suggest the names of advocates who can fight for her rights. Sometimes they can settle the matter by counseling both the victim and her husband and in-laws. Counseling is an important tool for the victim to help overcome the trauma, recover and rebuild their life. It provides a safe environment where the victim can work through their issues, helping to get their life back on track and be able to move on (Whelen, 1996).

Provide medical assistance: NGOs assist the victim women to get medical aid by the doctors. Doctors, both government and private have to provide first aid to the victim women without insisting on completion of legal formalities such as registration of crime.

Help to get financial assistance: Sometimes the destitute or deprived women want to empower financially by organizing a small scale unit or to earn by using their technical knowledge. In that situation the NGOs will help such women to get the bank loans or margin money from the welfare departments.

Provide skilled training: The NGOs provide vocational trainings, if the victim women require and request for it. Some NGOs run vocational schools for women and these women will be helped to get vocational training in such schools free of cost as these NGOs get aid from the government.

Provide Legal Aid and conducting Legal Literacy Camps: Many NGOs help the women who require legal services and also help the distressed women to know about the facilities of legal aids available for them to fight legally whenever they are

deprived of their conjugal rights due to domestic violence. These NGOs sometimes conduct legal literacy camps independently or with the collaboration of the Legal Services Authorities or other NGOs. In India many women due to the ignorance of the facilities, provided for them suffers domestic violence silently. So, the main aim of these legal literacy camps conducted by the NGOs is to educate the women about their basic human rights. If all the women are well aware of the legal provisions and availability of legal services, they can dare resist the atrocities and they even fight legally if need arises.

Protest by Public Interest Litigation: The court, permits public interest litigation or social interest litigations by “public spirited citizens” for the enforcement of constitutional and legal rights of distressed women who are unable to approach the court for relief. Many NGOs have started to emancipate women by public interest litigation.

Crisis Centers and Hotlines Crisis centers and hotlines provide support and counseling services to victims of violence. In many parts of the world, crisis centers and hotlines rely on trained volunteers to work with battered women. This type of assistance is based on the theory that women are the best judges of their own situations and support from peers rather than professional psychologists is an effective method of assisting the women in determining her best course of action.

While some organizations have reached out to affected women directly with legal aid, family intervention, alternative shelter, and economic programs providing income-generating opportunities, many others have refrained from tackling the issue of violence head on. Those organizations operating with an understanding of the structural nature of domestic violence seek to empower women through education, legal awareness, asset creation, and mobilization of strong women’s groups. Innovative methods to build community awareness and support include street plays, exhibitions, mass meetings, organizing elderly women to welcome every new bride to the village, and mock funeral processions publicizing violence (Grover, 1986). By attempting to make domestic

violence a part of public discourse, the NGO community has begun to deconstruct the myth of the private nature of the problem (Guha Roy, 1994).

NGOs in West Bengal

According to the a report, an NGO approached both the State Government and the State Human Rights Commission for raising concern over the rise in cases of cruelty in West Bengal against women by their husbands or relatives but low rates of conviction.

There are several NGOs working for distressed women in West Bengal for e.g. Swayam, Women’s Sahayog, Sanhita, Sachetna, All India Progressive Women’s Association etc. These are the Kolkata based women’s NGOs fighting against different crimes against women specially against domestic violence. These NGOs look at each women’s problem in a holistic way and try to give her as much support as possible. When the victim women of domestic violence are suffering from trauma, depression, acute anxiety or other psychological conditions, they are offered professional psychological counseling by these NGOs. They also provide confidential counseling to the victim. Therefore, NGOs for women generally provide direct support services to the domestic violence victims like counseling, legal aid, police follow up, referral for vocational training, short shelter homes and employment to women facing violence in their lives.

They also conduct awareness generation programme on the issue of violence against women including Domestic violence. Many NGOs do research and conduct campaigns, workshops, and seminars on the issues of violence against women especially domestic violence (Sanhita and UNIFEM, 2002).

Domestic violence- Intervention of Family Counselling Centres

The Family Counselling Centres (FCCs) were created by the Central Social Welfare Board (CSWB) out of its concern for growing atrocities against women. The Board saw the FCCs as agencies with

the potential for promoting harmony and thus preventing break-up of families. Under this scheme, voluntary agencies are supported for delivering out wide range of preventive, curative and rehabilitative services to women. The scheme of FCCs has been of existence since 1983 and is considered one of the most popular intervention programme to address cases of domestic violence against women (Jayaprakash Institute of Social Change, 2006).

Social Work Intervention: The injuries, trauma, stigma and psychological frustration associated with domestic violence call for social work intervention. If the interventions properly work then they can reduce future occurrence of domestic violence. Battered women need urgent attention or immediate care. The social workers have the responsibility of assisting such women with prompt treatment as soon as possible. Through counseling social workers could determine the cause of abuse, assisting them to build up the victim's self esteem and help them to decide what measures they want to take. Victims of domestic violence may be stigmatized or feel ashamed, their wounded ego needs to be boosted. To this end, social workers have the responsibility of reducing their emotional problems through psychological means such as words of encouragement, reassurance, advice and emotional support etc. Women need to understand the severity of domestic violence. Women need to be taught to re-evaluate their situation. The social workers have to educate the victims regarding various issues and legal interventions. The social workers should try to play the role of an advocate i.e. linking the victims of domestic violence with resources in their localities which can help in ameliorating their sufferings. They have the responsibilities of organizing a community wide education campaign which will help the community to become aware of the dangers of domestic violence and report cases of such abuses to the law enforcement agents as quickly as possible (Mojoyinola, 2006).

There exist high rates of domestic violence in the general population and in situations within which social workers have traditionally operated such as family service settings, mental health treatment settings and child welfare (Busby, 1996). But which

is very painful is that domestic violence lack proper recognition in our present society and accordingly an inadequate amount of importance given to the intervention of social workers. To investigate the issues such as prevalence, characteristics and treatment of domestic violence, social worker's intervention is essentially required. There is a dire need of a more integrated service delivery system on the community level particularly for the survivors of domestic violence. Principles of social work assessment includes the individual, family and community level information considered important for understanding the situation of the survivors, perpetrators or child witness of domestic violence. The most widely used method of social work is case work which is essentially used while treating domestic violence affected client. Counselors in various family counseling centers, family courts and legal aid services frequently apply principles, skills and techniques of social work profession while dealing persons affected with domestic violence. Even candidates with social work background are given preferences for being selected as Protection Officer. To identify the risk factors that have been empirically associated with causation of domestic violence including severe injuries, sexual assault, threat to kill, the involvement of drug and alcohol in the violence, history of severe violence in the family of origin etc. A social worker must use various methods of social work to acquire the information.

Social workers primary goal is to help the people in need and to address social problems, then use their knowledge, values and skills to address the social problem of domestic violence. They respect the inherent dignity and worth of the person, they treat both victims and perpetrators in a respectful manner.

Social workers must have insight into the problem of domestic violence to effectively work towards ending relationship violence. Social workers should be aware of the fact that like all crimes, the exact number of domestic violence assaults is hard to determine. Research indicates that an assault, at a criminal level occurs at least once in as many as 25-50% of all marriages. Domestic violence occurs at the micro level, affecting one family at a time, but it is also a macro problem which needs effective

intervention at all levels of social work practice. Social workers must be working at the community level that will create a society that is less tolerant of domestic violence (Sandel, 2003).

Conclusion

This study reveals that in spite of the fact that there are so many laws enacted, domestic violence is still wide spread in the society. Today, in India, especially in West Bengal, women are increasingly being educated and joining to perform different occupations but domestic violence like wife beating, physical and mental cruelty are continued still in elite classes also. This article shows that there are various causes of domestic violence which were not isolated from each other but often interplay of more than one causative factor. The consequences are also dependent on the capabilities and assets of the survivor and those with minimum of these two were the worst affected. The legal measures against dowry and domestic violence could not achieve the desired objectives because simply enacting laws cannot change the attitude of a large number of men (and women), socialized in a patriarchal culture.

The real problem, it seems, is the perceived internalized and socially reinforced ideology of the inferiority of women. Majority of women are also not aware of their rights due to lack of economic support, they are often unable to bear the cost of the judicial proceedings. It was also unfortunate to notice that often the investigation done by the State machinery, is so casual, negligent and defective, that allows the criminals of domestic violence to get away with their offence easily. The police generally try to patch up the whole case and are reluctant to register an F.I.R. In certain instances, police seem to be reluctant to act against any influential person (Ghosh, 2012).

The involvement of people from all walks of life and the consolidated efforts of professional from all the spheres of the society will be an important means to find a solution to the ever increasing menace of domestic violence.

Different NGOs are considering domestic violence as a heinous crime and according to these NGOs, any kind of domestic violence should not be condoned at any time. These NGOs are constantly encouraging the victim women to become self

confident, self sufficient and economically independent, because these NGOs believe that each and every woman possesses an inner strength to counter obstacles and thus emerge with renewed self confidence as a stronger and more complete woman. Through awareness programmes, campaigns, rallies, workshops etc. NGOs of today challenge the societal norms and values which perpetuate violence against women like Domestic Violence and influence public policy decisions that affect women's basic rights.

Social work intervention will be very important to deal with the massive impact of spousal violence. Spreading awareness among the rural women and sensitizing them about the various supportive legal measures available would help survivors in their fight for justice.

As social workers, it is important to confront the discrepancies between women's beliefs and actions regarding domestic violence in a supportive manner. Social workers must assist clients in acknowledging and addressing the numerous factors that influence the ways in which clients incorporate societal beliefs into their daily lives and the outcomes resulting from such actions. In respecting the experiences of clients, social workers must possess the ability to provide clients with unconditional positive regard and honor the stories being shared. When working with clients, social workers must possess the capacity to allow and support clients to make their own decisions, even when the decision is against the practitioner's own belief system (Mitra, 2000).

Intimate partner violence is a result of many contributing factors. Recognizing the underlying causes of domestic violence will allow social workers to address the issues more effectively while advocating for resources that may assist in mitigating the impact of domestic violence on victims. For Asian Americans, family is an important component and source of support. Any prevention and educational efforts by practitioners should involve family and friends of the victim. In doing so, victims are less likely to feel alienated and powerless in overcoming trauma incurred from intimate partner violence.

Women often remain in abusive relationships due to lack of resources and a lack of awareness about resources, which are available to assist women in leaving their abuser. Knowledge about community

resources is imperative in alleviating fears and stress victims often develop when deciding whether to leave or stay. An awareness of available resources may be a motivator for women hesitating to leave their abusive because of a lack of supportive services.

The responsibility of social workers is to educate and advocate on behalf of those that are marginalized. Just as social workers must advocate for victims, they must also educate men on adopting better coping strategies to handle conflicts without resorting to acts of violence. Asian American men and women are reluctant to seek assistance aside from family and friends due to stigma of being a victim or abuser. Practitioners must acknowledge the fear and commend clients that are courageous enough to seek assistance.

It is not gain-saying the fact that social workers have many important or useful roles to play in reducing and containing domestic violence. Their involvement in the prevention and management of domestic violence also go a long way in reducing its scourge in our midst or its economic costs for the government.

In order to reduce the curse of domestic violence in our midst, or reduces its economic costs, the following recommendations are hereby made, that, couples should nip their grievances or conflicts in the bud before getting out of hands, that the government or non-governmental organizations should help in creating job opportunities for social workers who will help in fighting the battle against family violence or unemployed youths and adults should be helped to ease their financial problems, thereby preventing crime and other antisocial behavior (Mojoyinola, 2006).

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